

The Influence of Product Quality and Content Marketing on Purchasing Decision in UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City

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Abstract: Medyna Hijab is one of the hijab and Muslim clothing manufacturers in Blitar, the development of this business is very rapid until now which is motivated by several factors including product quality, content marketing and purchasing decisions. This research aims to examine the effect of product quality and content marketing on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. The research method is quantitative. The scope of this study uses two independent variables, namely product quality (X1) and content marketing (X2), while the dependent variable used is the purchase decision (Y) at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. The population in this study were consumers who had purchased hijab products at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City, totaling 056 consumers. The sample calculation in this study used the slovin formula with a significant level of 10%. Significant level of 10%. So, a sample of 95 respondents was obtained. Researchers use purposive sampling. Data collection using a questionnaire with a Likert scale, interviews and documentation. Data analysis using multiple linear regression analysis and hypothesis testing consists of t test, F test and coefficient of determination test. coefficient of determination. The results of this study concluded that simultaneously the variables of product quality and content marketing have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This means that companies need to pay attention to product quality and content marketing to be able to improve purchasing decisions.

Keywords: Product Quality, Content Marketing, Purchasing Decision.

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1. Background of the study

The Muslim fashion industry has experienced rapid development as well as in Indonesia, which has the largest total population of 270 million people, 240.62 million of whom are Muslim (Annur, 2023). With the largest Muslim population, Indonesia is one of the target fashion markets targeted by the global market. This phenomenon creates business opportunities for the community, so that many business actors with similar products are ready to compete for a wide market coverage. The presence of these business actors has had a significant impact on the trade and industry sector, including Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) (Tasikmalaya, 2023).

MSMEs are one of the important pillars in economic development in Indonesia that must continue to be promoted so that they can compete, contribute more to the economy, and absorb more labor. Where the contribution of MSMEs to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is 61%, or valued at IDR 9,580 trillion, and their contribution to employment has reached 97% of the total workforce (Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2023).

Marketing strategies and sales methods such as utilizing social media for marketing facilities. In addition, business actors must focus on improving product quality to be able to compete with competitors with the same type of product. According to Kotler & Keller (2016:179) Consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. Purchasing decisions are inseparable from how the nature of a consumer (consumer behavior) so that each consumer has different habits in making purchases. As for the indicators of purchasing decisions, namely product choice, brand choice, choice of purchase channel, purchase time and purchase amount (Kotler & Keller, 2016:183).

One of the factors that is key to the business success in improving purchasing decisions is product quality. According to Kotler & Keller (2016: 37) product quality is a product's ability to perform its functions, these capabilities include durability, reliability, accuracy, which the product gets as a whole. Companies must be able to improve the quality of their products or services because improving product quality can make customers feel satisfied with the products or services provided and will influence

customers to repurchase these products. Product quality indicators can be measured through performance, features, reliability, conformity to specifications, durability and design (Sangadji & Sopiah, 2016: 80). The results of research from Kasno et al (2023), Satria (2023), Tukuboya (2023) state that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

Another factor that can influence purchasing decisions is content marketing. To be able to increase sales in today's digital marketing era, companies must be able to provide attractive marketing content for their customers. The content created must be interesting, unique and contain information about the product to be sold. Milhinhos (2015: 7) suggests that content marketing is a technique for creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and acquire a clear audience with the aim of driving profitable customer interest. There are six indicators of content marketing, namely: relevant, accuracy, value, easy to understand, easy to find and consistent. The results of research from Vildayanti et al (2022) and Cahyaningtyas & Wijaksana (2021) and Susilawati & Wulantika (2023) state that content marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

UKM Medyna Hijab is one of the hijab and clothing manufacturers in Blitar, founded by Novita Ike Triyuliani since 2018. UKM Medyna Hijab is located in Papungan Village, Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency. Based on the results of observations that have been made, the products sold by UKM Medyna Hijab have good product quality. UKM Medyna Hijab pay great attention to the quality of the hijab materials they use, such as polyester and voal which make the hijab comfortable, lightweight and give a casual impression when worn, and are suitable for young people to adults. UKM Medyna Hijab also provides various kinds of hijab from various brands such as umama scarf, Medyna scarves, Qairina, Inara etc. UKM Medyna Hijab always provides an up to date hijab collection according to customer needs and desires.

UKM Medyna Hijab uses various marketing strategies to be able to reach a wider range of customers, from teenagers to adults. The number of competitors with the same product and quality, makes Medyna Hijab SMEs use a marketing strategy by creating content on social media such as Instagram, namely with 3 - 5 contents a day. In addition, UKM Medyna Hijab also pays attention to the correlation between feeds and the quality of content to produce interesting posts. This aims to reach the intended target audience, namely the age group 17 to 30 years and above.

UKM Medyna Hijab always makes aesthetic content marketing by harmonizing the color of each photo or video, content background, type of photo or video of the product offered and tidying up the appearance of the @medyna_hijab Instagram feeds. In the content marketing made by UKM Medyna Hijab, it also provides a clear description of the products promoted through Instagram in the form of audio and text starting from the type of fabric, clothing size and price so as not to cause disappointment to consumers when making purchases directly at the UKM Medyna Hijab store.

Table 1. Data on Total Sales of Hijab Products at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City

No.	Mounth	Sales Quantity of Hijab Products (pcs)	Percentage (%)
1.	Juni	2.064	36
2.	Juli	1.560	24
3.	Agustus	1.860	19
4.	September	1.797	3
5.	Oktober	1.787	0,5
6.	November	1.287	28

Source: UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City (2023)

However, there is a phenomenon in UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City, which in the last 3 months has experienced a decline in sales of hijab products. In June - July 2023 sales decreased by 24% because during the school vacation season people prefer to allocate their budget for recreational activities and after Idul Fitri the need for hijab decreased because it had been fulfilled in the previous month. In August there are usually many discounts offered in commemoration of the Independence Day of the Republic of Indonesia and also many new hijab product collections resulting in a 19% increase in sales. However, in September - November 2023 experienced a decline in sales with the biggest decline occurring in November by 28% due to delays in the availability of some product stock.

In addition, the decline in sales was also caused by promotional activities carried out by UKM Medyna Hijab which focused more on promoting clothing products than the hijab, so that the content marketing created made consumers only focus on their clothing products. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on "The Effect of Product Quality and Content Marketing on Purchasing Decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City".

2. Literature Review

2.1 Product Quality

According to Kotler & Keller (2016:37) Product quality is a product's ability to perform its functions, these capabilities include durability, reliability, accuracy, which the product gets as a whole. Companies must be able to improve the quality of their products or services because improving product quality can make consumers feel satisfied with the products or services provided and will influence customers to repurchase these products. Indrasari (2019:87) states that product quality, namely consumers will feel satisfied if the results of their evaluation show that the products they use are of quality. The indicators of product quality can be measured through performance, features, reliability, conformity to specifications, durability and design (Sangadji & Sopiah, 2016:80)

2.2 Content Marketing

According to Milhinhos (2015:7) content marketing is a technique for creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and acquire a clear audience with the aim of driving profitable customer interest. Meanwhile, Pulizi (2014:22) argues that content marketing is a marketing process for creating and distributing valuable and interesting content to attract, acquire and engage a clear and understood target audience so as to encourage customers to take actions that provide benefits.

The indicators of content marketing, namely: relevant, accurate, valuable, easy to understand, easy to find and consistent (Milhinhos, 2015).

2.3 Purchasing Decision

According to Kotler & Keller (2016:179) Consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. Purchasing decisions are inseparable from how the nature of a consumer (consumer behavior) so that each consumer has different habits in making purchases. Firmansyah (2019:205) states that buying decisions are problem-solving activities carried out by individuals in selecting appropriate alternative behaviors from two or more alternative behaviors and are considered the most appropriate action in buying by first going through the stages of the decision-making process. Meanwhile, Indrasari (2019:70) purchasing decisions are individual activities that are directly involved in making decisions to make purchases of products offered by sellers. As for the indicators of purchasing decisions, namely product choice, brand choice, choice of purchase channel, purchase time and purchase amount (Kotler & Keller, 2016:183).

2.4 Hypothesis of the study

Figure 1. Conceptual research

Source: Processed data (2023)

The hypothesis of this research is as follows:

H1: Product quality partially has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City.

H2: Content marketing partially has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City.

H3: Product quality and content marketing simultaneously have a positive effect on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City.

3. Research Methodology

The scope of this research is the independent variables which include product quality (X1) and content marketing (X2), while the dependent variable is the purchase decision (Y). The type of research in this study is explanatory research with a quantitative approach, which aims to test the proposed hypothesis, so that it is hoped that from this study researchers can explain the relationship and influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable in the hypothesis. The population in this study were consumers who purchased hijab products at UKM Medyna Hijab from June to November 2023, totaling 2,056 consumers. To determine the number of samples used the Slovin formula with a

significance level of 10%. So that a sample size of 95 respondents was obtained.

In this study, sampling used purposive sampling, where sampling in research uses certain considerations, measures, and criteria that have been determined by the researcher before the research process is carried out. The research data comes from distributing questionnaires directly to consumers of UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City who have purchased hijab products and follow the @medyna_hijab Instagram account. Secondary data sources are obtained from e-books, articles, journals, previous research reports and the internet related to the problem to be studied. The variables analyzed in this study include two independent variables, namely product quality (X1) and content marketing (X2), while the dependent variable is the purchase decision (Y). The scale used in this study is a Likert scale. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire distributed directly to respondents, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis uses several stages, namely descriptive analysis which aims to describe the demographic data of respondents and describe the answers of respondents to UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. Then, the instrument data test includes validity test, reliability test, classical assumption test which includes normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. Then multiple linear analysis and hypothesis testing which consists of the coefficient of determination (R²) test, t test and F test.

4. Results and Discussions

1. Characteristics of respondents based on age

The characteristics of respondents based on age can be divided into 4 categories, namely 17-20 years, 21-25 years, 26-30 years and >30 years. The following is respondent data based on age:

Table 2. Characteristics of respondents based on age

No.	Age	Amount	
		Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
1.	17-20 Years	16	16,8
2.	21-25 Years	58	61,1
3.	26-30 Years	15	15,8
4.	>30 Years	6	6,3
Total		95	100

Source: Processed data (2024)

Based on the results of table 1, it shows that most of the respondents with the highest number, namely in the age range of 21-25 years, were 58 people or 61.1%. This is because the 21-25 age range has a high tendency to use social media. In addition, they more often carry out online product search or purchase activities. Meanwhile, most of the respondents with the lowest number, namely in the age range > 30 years, were 6 people or 6.3%. This is because the age range > 30 years has a low use of social media. In addition, they also tend to do product search or purchase activities directly. So, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of UKM Medyna Hijab are dominated by consumers aged 21-25 years.

2. Characteristics of respondents based on employment status

The characteristics of respondents based on occupation can be divided into 3 categories, namely housewives, civil servants / self-

employed and students / students. The following is respondent data based on occupation:

Table 3. Characteristics of respondents based on employment status

No.	Work	Amount	
		Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
1.	Housewife	17	17,9
2.	Civil servants/self-employed	20	21,1
3.	Student	58	61,1
Total		95	100

Source: Processed data (2024)

Based on table it shows that most of the respondents with the highest number, namely with jobs as students, were 58 people or 61.1%. This is because students have quite high fashion needs and are more open to changes in fashion trends. Meanwhile, most of the respondents with the lowest number, namely Housewives (IRT) were 17 people or 17.9%. This is because housewives have low fashion needs and are less open to changes in fashion trends. So, it can be concluded that most of the respondents of UKM Medyna Hijab are dominated by consumers with jobs as students.

4.1 Validity Test

Table 4. Validity Test Result

Variable	Item	R count	R table	Sig.	Description
Product Quality (X1)	X1.1.1	0.771	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.1.2	0.734	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.2.1	0.792	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.2.2	0.732	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.3.1	0.752	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.3.2	0.700	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.4.1	0.666	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.4.2	0.705	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.5.1	0.740	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.5.2	0.767	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.6.1	0.765	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X1.6.2	0.742	0.1698	0.000	VALID
Content Marketing (X2)	X2.1.1	0.724	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.1.2	0.698	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.2.1	0.750	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.2.2	0.778	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.3.1	0.675	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.3.2	0.756	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.4.1	0.807	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.4.2	0.778	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.5.1	0.726	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.5.2	0.767	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.6.1	0.793	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	X2.6.2	0.764	0.1698	0.000	VALID
Purchasing Decision (Y)	Y1.1.1	0.632	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.1.2	0.736	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.1.3	0.703	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.2.1	0.772	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.2.2	0.714	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.2.3	0.710	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.3.1	0.756	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.3.2	0.681	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.4.1	0.645	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.4.2	0.689	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.5.1	0.645	0.1698	0.000	VALID
	Y1.5.2	0.722	0.1698	0.000	VALID

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the validity test results show that all statement items used as measuring instruments in this study include product quality variables (X1), content marketing (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) are valid.

4.2 Reliability Test

Table 5. Reliability Test Result

Variabel	Cronbach Alpha	Standar	Keterangan
Kualitas Produk (X1)	0.924	> 0,70	Reliabel
Content Marketing (X2)	0.929	> 0,70	Reliabel
Keputusan Pembelian	0.903	> 0,70	Reliabel

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the reliability test results show that all variables consisting of product quality, content marketing and purchasing decisions have a Cronbach alpha value > 0.70. This means that the statement items used in this study are reliable. Reliable means that the variable items of product quality (X1), content marketing (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) are considered reliable and reliable as variable measuring instruments in research.

4.3 Classic Assumption Test

4.3.1 Normality Test

In research, the normality test is used to test whether in the regression model, confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution. The normality picture can be shown as follows:

Figure 2. Normality Test Result

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the picture above, it can be seen that the distribution of data (points) is around the diagonal line and the distribution follows the direction of the diagonal line. So it can be concluded that the regression model fulfills the assumption of normality.

4.3.2 Multicollinearitas Test

In research, the multicollinearity test is used to test whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. The multicollinearity table can be shown as follows:

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test Result

Model	Collinearity		Description
	Tolerance	VIF	
Product Quality (X1)	0,393	2,543	Free of Multicollinearity Symptoms
Content Marketing (X2)	0,393	2,543	Free of Multicollinearity Symptoms

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it is known that the results of the multicollinearity test show the tolerance and VIF values are at tolerance 0.393 > 0.10 and VIF 2.543 < 10.00. Thus, the independent variables can be said to have no multicollinearity (assumptions met).

4.3.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

In research, the heteroscedasticity test is used to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance for all observations. The heteroscedasticity picture can be shown as follows:

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the picture above, it can be seen that the scatterplot display diagram spreads and does not form a certain pattern, the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, so it can be concluded that this model does not have heteroscedasticity symptoms.

4.3.4 Analysis Multiple Linear Regression

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
(Constant)	1,005	2,241
Product Quality (X1)	0,436	0,066
Content Marketing (X2)	0,522	0,066

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the multiple linear regression analysis test results can be known linear regression equations as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 1,005 + 0,436X_1 + 0,522X_2 + e$$

Based on the above equation, it can be explained as follows:

1. Constant Value (a) = 1.005

A constant of 1.005 means that the independent variables consisting of product quality (X1) and content marketing (X2) are ignored or assumed to be zero, then the purchasing decision variable (Y) will be equal to its constant value of 1.005.

2. Product Quality Variable Regression Coefficient Value (b1)

The multiple linear regression coefficient value of product quality (X1) of 0.436 is positive. This means that if there is an increase in value by 1 unit in the product quality variable and the other independent variables are zero, the purchasing decision variable (Y) will increase by 0.436. So it can be concluded that the product quality variable has a positive influence on purchasing decisions.

3. Content Marketing Variable Regression Coefficient Value (b2)

The multiple linear regression coefficient value of content marketing (X2) of 0.522 is positive. This means that if there is an increase in value by 1 unit in the content marketing variable and the other independent variables are zero, the purchasing decision variable (Y) will increase by 0.522. So it can be concluded that the content marketing variable has a positive influence on purchasing decisions.

4.3.5 Determinant Analysis (R²)

The coefficient of determination analysis is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain variations in the dependent variable. The table of results of the coefficient of determination analysis can be shown as follows:

Table 8. Results of the Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,916	0,838	0,835	2,642

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the adjusted coefficient (Adjusted R. Square) is 0.835. This means that the variance in the value of the purchasing decision variable (Y) of 83.5% is determined by the product quality and content marketing variables, the remaining 16.5% is influenced by other variables that are unknown and not examined in this study.

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

4.4.1 Partial Significant Test (t Test)

Table 9. t Test Result

Variable	t _{count}	t _{table}	Sig.	Significance Level (α)	Description
Product Quality (X1)	6,595	1,662	0,000	0,05	Significant
Content Marketing (X2)	7,921	1,662	0,000	0,05	Significant

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the partial test results in the table above, it can be concluded that:

1. The answer to H1 based on the test results of the product quality variable (X1) obtained the value $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $6.595 > 1.662$ with a probability of a significant value t of $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus the product quality variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Y) at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City.
2. The answer to H2 based on the test results of the content marketing variable (X2) obtained the value $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $7.921 > 1.662$ with a probability of a significant value t of $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus the content marketing variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Y) at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City

4.4.2 Symultant Significant Test (F Test)

Table 10. F Test Result

F count	F table	Sig.	Significance Level (α)	Description
238,506	3,095	0,000	0,05	Signifikan

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic v 25, processed data (2024)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the calculated F value is $238.506 > 3.095$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that the product quality variable (X1) and content marketing (X2) simultaneously have a positive effect on purchasing decisions (Y) at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City.

4.5 Discussion

The discussion in this study is based on the results of data analysis obtained from respondents' answers.

4.5.1 The Effect of Product Quality on Purchasing Decision

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of product quality variables, the indicator of conformity to specifications has the highest average value of 4.32. It can be interpreted that the average respondent agrees with the indicator of conformity to specifications. Respondents feel that UKM Medyna Hijab can provide prices that match the quality of the products offered and can provide clear product specifications to make it easier for consumers to make purchasing decisions.

Based on the results of the partial hypothesis test data analysis that has been carried out on the product quality variable, it can be seen that the product quality variable has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. This can be proven from the t test results, namely t_{count} of $6.595 > t_{table}$ 1.662 with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because there is an item with the largest average value on the product quality variable, namely the specification item. The specification item has the highest mean of 4.37 and can be classified in the very high mean category.

4.5.2 The Effect of Content Marketing on Purchasing Decision

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of content marketing variables, the easy-to-find indicator has the highest average value of 4.26. It can be interpreted that the average respondent agrees with the easy-to-find indicator. UKM Medyna Hijab uses Instagram social media to introduce its products and reach a wider audience. has product content that is easy to reach and is available on several social media such as Instagram and Tiktok. So that this makes it easier for consumers to obtain information about products as an alternative in making purchasing decisions.

Based on the partial hypothesis test data analysis that has been carried out on the content marketing variable, it can be seen that the content marketing variable has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. This can be proven from the t test results, namely t_{count} of $7.921 > t_{table}$ 1.662 with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This is because there are items with the largest average value on the content marketing variable, namely the easy-to-reach item. The easy-to-reach item has the highest mean of 4.29 and can be classified in the very high mean category.

4.5.3 The Effect of Product Quality and Content Marketing on Purchasing Decisions

This study has obtained results that show that product quality and content marketing simultaneously affect purchasing decisions. This can be proven based on the results of the analysis of the coefficient of determination with (Adjusted R. Square) of 0.835 or 83.5%. This means that the contribution made by the product quality and content marketing variables to purchasing decisions is

83.5%. The remaining 16.5% is influenced by other variables that are unknown and not examined in this study.

4.6 Implication

4.6.1 Theoretical Implication

The theoretical implications in this study are supported by the theory of product quality as stated by (Kotler & Keller (2016: 37) which defines that Product quality is a product's ability to perform its functions, that ability includes durability, reliability, accuracy, which is obtained by the product as a whole. Companies must be able to improve the quality of their products or services because improving product quality can make consumers feel satisfied with the products or services provided and will influence customers to repurchase these products. This research was developed by adding content marketing variables to purchasing decisions stated by Milhinhos (2015: 7) that "Content Marketing is a technique for creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and obtain a clear audience with the aim of driving profitable customer interest."

The results of this study indicate that the product quality variable has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Furthermore, the content marketing variable has a positive effect on purchasing decisions.

The results of this study strengthen the results of previous research by Tukuboya (2023) which states that product quality on purchasing decisions has a positive and significant effect. Meanwhile, the results of Susilawati & Wulantika's research (2023) state that content marketing on purchasing decisions has a positive and significant effect. Then the results of research by Devanny et al (2022) state that product quality and content marketing on purchasing decisions simultaneously have a positive and significant effect.

4.6.2 Practical Implication

The results of this study indicate that the product quality variable has a positive and significant effect, the content marketing variable has a positive and significant effect, product quality and content marketing simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study strengthen the results of previous research by Tukuboya (2023) which states that product quality on purchasing decisions has a positive and significant effect. Meanwhile, the results of Susilawati & Wulantika's research (2023) state that content marketing on purchasing decisions has a positive and significant effect. Then the results of research by Devanny et al (2022) state that product quality and content marketing on purchasing decisions simultaneously have a positive and significant effect.

4.6.3 Implications for Future Research

For future researchers who will conduct research related to purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City, they should conduct research with different independent variables

because there are many factors that influence purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City such as price, service quality, product diversity, promotion, and others. However, if future researchers are interested in conducting research related to product quality and content marketing on purchasing decisions, it is hoped that they will conduct research with different objects and use other indicators, so that they can perfect and evaluate existing theories for future research.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research that has been conducted, the results show that product quality and content marketing affect purchasing decisions. By going through various stages of validity and reliability tests as well as the t test and F test, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. There is a partial effect of product quality on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. This means that in order to improve purchasing decisions, excellent product quality is needed, this includes performance, features, reliability, conformity to specifications, durability and design.
2. There is a partial effect of content marketing on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. This means that to be able to improve purchasing decisions, very good content marketing is needed, this includes relevance, accuracy, value, easy to understand, easy to find and consistent.
3. There is a simultaneous influence of product quality and content marketing on purchasing decisions at UKM Medyna Hijab Blitar City. This means that to be able to improve purchasing decisions, excellent product quality and content marketing are needed.

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